

Demonstrating Elastic Stability Theory

From Lecture Notes to Demonstration Models

**Peter Charlton
Hertford College**

Supervisor: Paul Taylor

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1. Abstract

The aim of this project was to design and manufacture two demonstration models to aid the teaching of Elastic Stability Theory. It also aimed to investigate the extent to which their behaviour, as predicted by the theory and as found by testing the prototype models, imitates the behaviour of real structures. The two models chosen to be constructed were the single-degree-of-freedom tied arch and a spring and link model with a bilinear response.

The two demonstration models imitate two of the six theoretical mechanisms used in the lectures on Elastic Stability Theory in the fourth year of the Engineering Science course at Oxford University. The first six lectures of this course aim to give an understanding of elastic displacements of plates and shells. The final two lectures aim to give an appreciation of the limitations of the theories of bending and stretching, using the theoretical mechanisms. The prototype models designed and manufactured in this project aim to help students to visualise the mechanisms, and watch their behaviour in reality.

The mechanisms, and prototypes which imitate them, are useful because they exhibit “generic properties of more realistic and complicated structures (like plates and shells)”¹, as shown by Elastic Stability Theory, whilst their behaviour is much easier to understand and predict than that of real-world structures. Their behaviour is often unwanted in real-world structures, and can lead to catastrophic failure, demonstrating the importance of the effects of imperfections and buckling when designing structures containing plates and shells. These mechanisms aim to help students to avoid this behaviour when designing structures, and aim to demonstrate the potential pitfalls associated with the linear and weakly non-linear theory of elastic stability, particularly the dangers of imperfections.

This report includes:

- The behaviour of the theoretical mechanisms, as predicted by elastic stability theory.
- The desired behavioural characteristics of each prototype model.
- The design and manufacturing process undertaken to construct each prototype.
- The testing of each prototype, and the conclusions of the tests.
- Tests carried out on an arch, to compare the behaviour of this structure to that predicted by theory and shown by the two prototypes.

2. Acknowledgements

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¹ (Taylor, 2009), lecture 7, p.1

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4. The Tied Arch Model

4.1 Overview

The single-degree-of-freedom tied arch is the first mechanism used to demonstrate elastic stability theory in the lecture series². The first prototype was designed to imitate this mechanism. Much of its design work was useful for the spring and link prototype, as they share similar components. The mechanism is shown in Figure 1:

Figure 1: The theoretical single-degree-of-freedom tied arch.³

Q_1 is the single generalised co-ordinate of the system; α is the value of Q_1 at which no force (P) is required for equilibrium; k is the spring's stiffness and L is the length of the rigid links.

Assumptions

The assumptions given in Table 1 are made when analysing this mechanism. They must be appreciated to predict its behaviour. These assumptions also apply to the spring and link mechanism.

Component	Assumptions
Rigid link of length L	Inextensible, rigid
Spring of stiffness k	Spring acts linearly in compression and tension, for all values of extension
Force of magnitude P	A point force of constant magnitude (therefore no inertial forces are experienced, such as would be incurred with a hanging weight).
Environment	No drag, gravitational or frictional forces; closed, reversible system.

Table 1: The assumptions associated with the components of the tied arch mechanism.

These assumptions allow the mechanisms to be analysed using techniques already covered by the undergraduate course. This highlights the value of the mechanisms. They show the generic properties of elastic structures, whilst being accessible to undergraduates. An aim when designing and manufacturing the prototypes was to minimise their deviation from these assumptions.

² (Taylor, 2009), lecture 7, p.2

³ A modified version of a diagram from (Taylor, 2009), lecture 7, p.2, which was originally sourced from (Thompson & Hunt, Elastic Instability Phenomena, 1984), p.61

Analysis of the theoretical mechanism

For the tied arch mechanism, elastic stability theory shows that:⁴

$$\text{Strain energy in spring, } U = 2kL^2(\cos Q_1 - \cos \alpha)^2$$

Equation 1

$$\text{Downwards deflection of dead load, } E_p = L(\sin \alpha - \sin Q_1)$$

Equation 2

$$\text{Total potential energy of system, } V = U - PE_p \quad (\text{a constant})$$

Equation 3

To analyse the system's behaviour, only the solutions for which the mechanism is in equilibrium are relevant. At these, there is no local change in the system's potential energy with respect to position, so a small disturbance will not change the energy state of the system. Furthermore, a prototype contains positive definite damping so that small disturbances will be dissipated through damping mechanisms.⁵

Therefore all equilibrium positions of the mechanism satisfy:

$$\frac{dV}{dQ_1} = 0$$

Equation 4

Substituting in Equation 1, Equation 2 and Equation 3 into Equation 4:

$$\text{Force at equilibrium, } P = 4kL(\cos Q_1 - \cos \alpha) \tan Q_1$$

Equation 5⁶

The two equilibrium positions for which no force, P, is required to keep the structure in equilibrium are given by $Q_1 = \pm\alpha$. The upper value is illustrated in Figure 1. The collection of equilibrium positions (called an equilibrium path) can now be plotted as a function of Q_1 , as shown in Figure 2:

Figure 2: The equilibrium path for the theoretical tied arch⁷

⁴ (Taylor, 2009), lecture 7, pp.2-3; originally taken from (Thompson & Hunt, 1984), chapter 4

⁵ Many of these ideas are from (Thompson & Hunt, 1984), chapter 1

⁶ (Thompson & Hunt, 1984), chapter 4

This figure shows the points at which the structure is in equilibrium with zero load applied (B, D and G). The behaviour shown is particularly characteristic of that predicted by elastic stability theory. For instance, the most useful aspect of the tied arch's behaviour is shown, the dynamic snap through.

$$\frac{dP}{dQ_1} = 0, \text{ at the critical points, C and F } \quad (\neq 0, \text{ elsewhere })$$

Equation 6

This occurs at a change in stability of the system from stable equilibrium (with a positive derivative, given by Equation 6 and shown by a solid path in Figure 2) to unstable equilibrium (with a negative derivative, shown by a dashed path). These points are known as critical points, because when the load reaches the critical loads of these points, the structure changes behaviour dramatically on encountering an unstable region of the equilibrium path. The structure becomes unstable and snaps through to the next stable region of the equilibrium path. If the load applied does not change during this snap, the system will snap from C to H, or F to A. In structural engineering, this may lead to catastrophic failure. In contrast, movement within a stable section of the equilibrium path is acceptable subject to the deformation remaining within the serviceability limit states.

The stability of an equilibrium position is determined by the second energy derivative:

$$\text{Second energy derivative} = \frac{d^2V}{dQ_1^2}$$

Equation 7

It is important to note that Equation 7 is exactly equivalent to Equation 6.

4.2 Relevance

Thompson has documented an extensive range of contexts in which elastic stability theory can be used to model man-made and natural systems⁸. It is important to be able to demonstrate the catastrophic capabilities of the snap-through which would be shown by a tied-arch prototype, because this behaviour makes the theory particularly applicable to many of these systems. There are many examples in structural engineering, some of which are explored in this report.

Outside of structural engineering, an interesting example of the application of elastic stability theory is “the bifurcational response of an animal when subjected simultaneously to rage and fear”⁹. Zeeman presented this model, suggesting that when an animal's rage and fear increase to sufficiently high levels, its response can snap between attack and flight, depending on the ‘quantities’ of rage and fear present. This response is modelled by a cusp catastrophe. When one parameter of a cusp catastrophe

⁷ Modified from (Thompson & Hunt, 1984) p.62

⁸ (Thompson J. , Instabilities and Catastrophes in Science and Engineering, 1982)

⁹ (Thompson J. , Instabilities and Catastrophes in Science and Engineering, 1982), p.17

is kept constant, the shape of the equilibrium path (given by a cross-section is taken of the cusp's equilibrium surface) is the same as that predicted for the tied arch. Thus, the arch's behaviour is an example of the much more general field of catastrophe theory.¹⁰

4.3 Design Criteria

The prototype model must display approximately the same behavioural traits as the theoretical tied arch. Qualitatively, the traits are:

- The arch supports itself at a constant positive value of Q_1 (say β) and a constant negative value of Q_1 (say γ). (Note that in the prototype, $\beta \neq \alpha$)
- For $Q_1 > \beta$, the arch requires an upwards force to support it.
- For $Q_1 < \gamma$, the arch requires a downwards force to support it.
- When the structure is force-controlled, rather than displacement-controlled, it exhibits snap-through at a critical force, which occurs at a constant critical angle.

Quantitatively, the following traits would ideally be shown:

- The arch supports itself at angles $Q_1 \approx \pm\alpha$.
- Therefore the above conditions are satisfied with $\beta \approx \alpha$ and $\gamma \approx -\alpha$.
- The equilibrium path can be predicted using a modified version of the theoretical mechanism. This would include additional terms in Equation 3 to compensate for any unreasonable assumptions made by the theoretical model.

4.4 Design and Manufacturing considerations

Initially, a preliminary prototype model was constructed for the tied arch. This is shown in Figure 3:

Figure 3: The preliminary prototype model of the tied arch

This model supported itself at a constant angle, and it snapped through when a certain critical force was applied. Lessons learnt from this model included:

- The rigid links in the theoretical mechanism were replaced by 3D planks. The dimensions used (15x150x450 mm) were large enough for the planks to be clearly seen in a lecture theatre.

¹⁰ (Saunders, 1980)

- Two adjacent hinges were used to join the planks, and to join each plank to its support. It was very difficult to align their hinge rods in exactly the same direction, and in practice the use of two hinges introduced much friction.
- The friction between the supports and a table top (whether wooden or synthetic) was too great for the tied arch to easily move. A method of reducing this friction would have to be found.
- The model was only able to function until it deflected downwards slightly past its flat position for two reasons. Firstly, the planks were too closely joined, and when this maximum angle of inflection was reached the sides of the planks collided, preventing the arch inverting any further. Secondly, the spring could not act in compression, because it was an extensional spring, and because it was attached to the arch using string which cannot carry tensile forces.

The design was adapted to avoid these problems in the final prototype model. Some improvements are shown in Figure 4, a developed design for the prototype. The other changes required to avoid the initial problems are gradually brought into the design over the following pages.

Figure 4: A developed design of the tied arch model

Improvements to the model include:

- The use of two rails along which one end of the arch can slide using ‘travelling rods’, whilst the other is fixed. The gap between the rails allows the arch to snap through between the rails.
- The spring between the rigid links has been split into two springs, one on either side of the planks. This is to avoid the turning moment that would be applied to the central hinge by a single spring on one side of the planks. The total stiffness of the replacement springs is equivalent to that of the single spring in the original model.
- ‘End clamps’ have been used to attach the springs to the planks, instead of string, allowing compressive forces to be transmitted. An end-clamp is shown in Figure 10 (p.16).

The planks

The 3D planks shown in Figure 4 (and those for the spring and link model) were made from MDF so that holes could be quickly drilled to alter the design whilst trialling the prototype model. The dimensions used for the initial prototype’s planks were used for the final prototype too. The thickness

of 15mm provided adequate bending stiffness and adequate thickness to avoid splitting the wood. It was thought that these dimensions were a good compromise between being large enough to be easily seen from a reasonable distance, and giving the smallest possible mass of wood.

The rods

Cylindrical travelling rods sliding along rails were chosen as a method allowing the tied arch to move as freely as possible. It was decided that both the rails and the rods would be mild steel, to give a low coefficient of friction.¹¹ It was desirable to have the smallest possible diameter rods to keep their mass as low as possible, and to reduce the size of the bosses used for the clamps, further reducing mass and the required machining. Mild steel rods of diameter 3/16" (4.76mm) were used as this was the smallest diameter which gave sufficiently stiff rods.

The hinges

Two types of hinges were used in the design and manufacture of the tied-arch.

Referring to Figure 4, the first type was used for the central hinge joining the two planks. It was important for this hinge to be an orthodox hinge, so that the audience could immediately understand how the planks were joined. It also had to allow the maximum possible inversion of the arch. To achieve this the hinge needed to rotate through the greatest possible angle, and it needed to allow the two planks to be attached as far from each other as possible so that they would not reduce the possible angle of inversion, as they did in the preliminary prototype model. A parliament hinge was found to give the greatest range of angular movement, and allowed the planks to be mounted on the hinge furthest away from each other. Two parliament hinges were bought externally, and were attached to the planks using countersunk bolts and nuts, rather than screws, to avoid splitting the planks. This worked well, although it was important to file down the contact points between the two halves of the hinge to reduce the moment required to turn the hinge.

The second type of hinge was required to secure a travelling rod to the outer ends of the planks (shown in Figure 4). For these, a new component was designed and manufactured. It is known as an ‘imperfectionator’, for reasons explained below, and is shown in Figure 5(a):

Figure 5: (a) the imperfectionator; (b) two imperfectionators used to secure a travelling rod onto a plank.

¹¹ To reduce the coefficient of friction further, the rods and rails were lubricated using ‘WD40’.

Figure 5(b) shows two imperfectionators being used as the second type of hinge. Also shown in this picture are two simple clamps, on either side of the plank, which are described in ‘The simple clamp’ section (p.17).

The imperfectionator was initially designed to allow a rod to be mounted at any point along the length of a plank. Slots were to be cut into the plank, parallel to its length so that the imperfectionators, and therefore the rod, could be attached at any point along the length of the plank. With this design, a force could be applied to the rod, and therefore the arch, at any point along the plank’s length. The tied-arch’s insensitivity to imperfections could then be easily tested by applying the force at various positions along the length of the plank. Ultimately, this test was not conducted due to time constraints. It was thought that the results of the test would be trivial¹², and would not give any additional insight into the accuracy of the tied arch prototype.

This raises an important point about the tied arch mechanism. The tied arch mechanism is not sensitive (above linear) to imperfections in its properties. This is in contrast to a high arch, which is imperfection sensitive, giving a very significant reduction in strength due to manufacturing imperfections. To investigate this behaviour, a similar experiment to that conducted on the tied arch prototype was also conducted on steel struts, detailed in section 5.

The demonstration and testing rig

A lecturer must be able to demonstrate the prototypes’ behaviour qualitatively in lectures. An operator must also be able to test their behaviour in a force-displacement testing machine. These processes will assess the prototypes’ ability to meet the design criteria. For both purposes an all-purpose rig was required to support the prototypes and provide the appropriate freedom for their movement. Only one rig would be designed and constructed, rather than one for each prototype, to save on time and costs.

To demonstrate the prototypes in a lecture, the rig had to satisfy the following:

- The safety of the operator and audience must be ensured at all times.
- The available apparatus is assumed to be a large flat surface, and therefore the rig must be able to sit on this surface.
- The prototype and rig must be portable by one person.
- It would be advantageous to be able to show the spring and link prototype in different orientations to allow the audience to see clearly how the different components interact.

The testing machine to be used was the ‘Instron 5582’ model. This machine applies a measured force to the apparatus whilst moving the point of application vertically at a chosen rate. It would be able to

¹² This test would simply reduce the downwards deflection of the force, changing the ‘L’ in Equation 2 to ‘L-d’, where d is the distance of the rod and therefore the point of force application from the central hinge in the arch. Therefore a greater force would be required to achieve equilibrium. This is supported by the tied arch’s insensitivity to imperfections (above linear).

follow the equilibrium paths of the tied-arch and spring and link prototypes precisely and accurately, as they are specified in force-displacement space.¹³ To allow the rig to be used in the machine to test the prototypes, the following were required:

- The safety of the operator must be maintained at all times of operation.
- The rig must be securely fixed to the machine for safety and for accurate measurement of the vertical displacement of the force.
- The rig must fit in the space between the arms of the Instron machine (590mm apart), and between the machine's base plate and the crosshead vertically above.
- The force must be applied by one of the available crosshead fixings.
- The rig must be rigidly attached to the machine's base plate. The relevant features of the base plate are illustrated in Figure 6. The figure shows the outline of the base plate, with the tapped holes available for fixings. All measurements are in millimetres.

Figure 6: The Instron machine's base plate (measurements in mm)

The rig had to conservatively allow for approximately 1.10m length of flat arch (including hinges) to snap through the centre of the rig, of approximate width 0.30m. It also had to provide two rails for the travelling rods to run along. Therefore, it was decided that the rig should be made from timber, to keep the manufacturing time low, and that mild steel strips would be overlaid on the timber rig to provide a mild steel surface for the rails. It was decided to also include crossbeams, giving the rig the shape of a frame, for torsional strength and additional stability. To fit this frame into the gap between the machine arms, when testing the tied-arch, the horizontal rig would have to be mounted with the edges holding the rails parallel to the vertical machine arm edges, shown in bold in Figure 6. This meant that the frame would stick out of the machine significantly.

For the tied arch and the arch in the spring and link prototype to be able to snap through, the rig had to be lifted well above the base plate. M16 mild steel studs, of length 0.5m, were to be used as legs to

¹³ The exception to this is if $k_1 > 4k_2$ for the spring and link model. (See Figure 28 (p.36) for an explanation. The equilibrium paths specified by these spring stiffnesses cannot be followed by the machine as that would require the machine to respond to the force measured with a change in direction, which it isn't able to do.

hold the rig above the plate. When these were fixed in the tapped holes of the base plate, there was negligible movement of the arms, giving a stable base for the rig elevated well above the base plate. This gave an extra requirement: the rig would be supported by four studs at points vertically above four of the tapped holes in Figure 6. The ideal distance between the rails of approximately 0.33m gave a wide enough hole to ensure that the tied-arch could not collide with the frame during snap-through. This was slightly too wide to overlay the four central tapped holes. In addition, the force applied by the Instron machine is vertically above the centre of its base plate. This force had to be applied to the centre of the prototypes, which had to lie in the middle of the rig. Therefore the rig could not be mounted off-centre, and the four outer tapped holes (1, 4, 5 and 8) had to be used to support the rig.

The studs had to pass through the frame's thickness so that nuts and washers could be used to secure the frame from above and below. This meant that they would protrude above the rails, and that travelling rods would not be able to pass over that part of the rails. Fortunately, this was not a problem for testing the tied arch on the Instron machine, as the arch would still be able to move through the necessary range of positions without the travelling rods colliding with the studs. However, it did mean that the design used must be adapted before being used for demonstrations (see the 'Adapting the rig for demonstration purposes' section on p.22 for further explanation).

The final design used for the frame is shown in exploded view in Figure 7:

Figure 7: The frame (exploded view)

Features to note include:

- The timber frame pieces are wider in the centre, where the stud holes are. There is additional thickness around the holes because the holes have reduced the thickness immediately around them. There is additional thickness between the holes because this is where the greatest bending moment will occur.
- The two holders drop into the appropriate holes in the rail and frame piece. A travelling rod can be placed through the gap in the centre of the holder to fix one end of the tied-arch prototype for use in lectures. This is necessary because the restraint provided by the Instron machine, preventing the central hinge from displacing horizontally, is no longer present in demonstrations.

- At the corners of the frame, the frame pieces interlock with the crossbeam. This gives some of the structural stiffness that would be given by triangulation, but is used here as a substitute because the hole in the centre of the frame must be free of obstructions.

The spring mechanism

Springs are crucial components to the teaching aids designed here. The tied-arch and the spring and link models use linear extensional springs. In contrast, the Augusti model, which is described in the ‘6.7 Further work’ section, uses torsional springs. In all three models, the springs must operate in both directions (in tension and compression, or in the case of torsion springs, in anticlockwise and clockwise directions) in order to give the full range of responses of the models.

There are three commonly available types of springs which appear to be suitable for these applications. Figure 8 shows the three types of springs in their unstressed state:

IMAGE REDACTED FOR COPYRIGHT PURPOSES

Figure 8: (a) an extension spring; (b) a compression spring; (c) a torsion spring¹⁴

It was important to understand the behaviour of each before being able to use them in the model designs. The key points are noted here.

The coils of the extension spring (a) touch in the unstressed state, therefore it can only be stretched in tension and cannot be compressed elastically. In contrast, the compression spring (b) can be extended or compressed from its unstressed state. To achieve this, the spring must be laterally restrained when under compression to prevent it from buckling¹⁵. The torsion spring (c) also allows movement in either direction. However, it is conventional to only allow the coils to be wound more tightly to give a reliable response.

This suggests that extension springs are not suitable, as they do not allow movement in both directions. Therefore, it was decided that for the tied-arch and the spring and link prototypes, laterally restrained compression springs would be used. For the Augusti prototype, either these, or torsion springs could be used, depending on the design. However, it was found that commercially available torsion springs do not allow the range of angular movement required by the Augusti mechanism. This was overcome by designing the prototype to use linear compression springs, by changing its angular rotation to a linear displacement, using a rack-and-pinion method.

¹⁴ (Ashfield Springs Ltd)

¹⁵ The springs used must be long to be seen clearly in a lecture theatre, and they must have a small diameter to fit into the designs. These demands ensure a slender spring, which is very susceptible to buckling unless a lateral restraint is present.

To use compression springs, a method of laterally restraining them had to be found. The two options were to place a casing around the springs, or to place a bar through the centre of the springs. Two dangers were that the additional casing or bar would make the spring mechanism significantly heavier, and that frictional ‘sticking points’ would be created between the coils and the casing or bar. The latter would be due to the change in diameter when springs are extended or compressed. Therefore, when either an internal bar or an external casing is used to restrain the spring, it must allow for this change in diameter. If a change in diameter is too great, then the spring’s behaviour is no longer reliable, either because of buckling or sticking points.

The remaining design issues were to attach the ends of the springs to the planks, and to keep the casings or internal rods secure. The final design addressed both these issues. This design securely attached rods to the planks using imperfectionators, and then the springs were attached to these rods using ‘mid-clamps’ (modified aluminium bosses). The method chosen is shown in Figure 9, attached to the tied arch prototype:

Figure 9: the manufactured spring mechanism, attached to the tied arch prototype

The key features of the manufactured spring mechanism are:

- One end of the internal rod is free to move through the mid-clamps, and one is fixed in place by a grub screw. In Figure 9, the left hand end is fixed and the right hand end is free to move.
- The spring is secured at each end using grub screws to clamp a length of uncoiled spring wire within its own hole, allowing tensile forces to be transferred. In Figure 9, this hole can be seen vertically above the hole used for the internal rod.
- The spring’s external diameter is larger than that of the hole in the mid-clamp for the internal bar, so the springs rest against the sides of the mid-clamps, allowing compressive forces to be transferred.
- The mid-clamp has a hole to attach it to the rod passing through the imperfectionators, with the rod fixed in place by a grub screw. This hole is perpendicular to the hole for the internal bar, and in Figure 9 it is below the internal bar.
- The mid-clamp is manufactured from a standard-sized aluminium boss for ease of manufacture.

This final design is a simplification of an original idea, which is documented on p.20, as it was eventually found that the behaviour of the original design may be closer to that of the theoretical linear spring than this final design (although it has its own disadvantages too).

The mid-clamp is crucial to this mechanism, and is shown more clearly in Figure 10(b), below. (a) shows the ‘end-clamp’, which was originally designed and manufactured for the spring mechanism. The one disadvantage of using the mid-clamp is that the direction of the spring’s force does not coincide with the direction of the rod passing through the imperfectionators. It was thought that the turning moment produced by this offset would lead to slip-stick friction of the internal rod against its casing in the clamp. However, in practice this was found not to be a problem, so the mid-clamp can always be used instead of end-clamps, and is preferred as it is more versatile.

Figure 10: (a) The end-clamp; (b) The mid-clamp

Applying the force to the tied-arch

The force had to be applied to the hinge of the tied-arch prototype by the Instron machine. This was achieved in two steps: Firstly adapting the hinge, and secondly designing and manufacturing a fixing to link the crosshead’s fixing to the hinge.

The hinge was adapted by simply removing the rod from the hinge, and replacing it with a longer 3/16” (4.76mm) diameter mild steel rod. This gave room on either side of the hinge for a force to be applied to the rod without interfering with the hinge’s movement. The diameter was chosen to give a snug, yet free-moving fit.

Figure 11(a) shows the lower part of the crosshead fixing which provided a rigid link between the Instron machine’s crosshead, and (b) shows the designed and manufactured fixing which linked the fixing shown in (a) to the hinge. (c) shows both parts in use whilst testing the tied-arch, although the crosshead fixing (as shown in (a)) is not visible because it is inside the other fixings.

Figure 11: (a) the most suitable crosshead fixing available; (b) manufactured fixing; (c) both being used to test the tied-arch

Figure 11(b) shows the manufactured fixing slightly differently to that in (c). (b) shows the setup used for applying a point force to a steel strip with a steel rod below and above the strip to provide both upwards and downwards forces. (c) shows the setup for testing the tied-arch, requiring only one rod. When designing the manufactured fixing, the following criteria were adhered to:

- Referring to Figure 11(b), dimension ‘A’ had to be large enough to surround the hinge, as shown in (c), but small enough to allow the spring mechanisms on either side of the planks to pass the ‘simple clamps’ at either end of the fixing’s rods without colliding with them. Dimension ‘B’ had to be large enough for two grub screws to fit across the component, but small enough so that the component would not collide with the planks when they were raised above the hinge rod.
- There had to be minimal compliance between the manufactured and crosshead fixings, and also within the manufactured fixing. The former was achieved by using a tapered bar (shown in (a)) to secure the two fixings with the tightest possible fit. The latter was achieved by using grub screws to make sure the components of the manufactured fixing were securely fixed together.
- Unlike the prototypes’, the fixing’s mass was not a concern as it would not affect the prototypes’ behaviour. Instead, the greatest concern was ease of manufacture. Thus its components were designed using standard-sized bars and bosses, with minimal machining required.

The simple clamp

The simple clamp was designed and manufactured to act as a clamp on a rod. It is a boss with a concentric hole passing through its centre, in which a rod can be clamped by a grub screw. One of its uses is illustrated in Figure 11(b) and (c). The clamp can also be used to guide travelling rods, by placing one clamp at each end of the rods, against the outer edge of each rail.

Modified theoretical model of behaviour

When the manufacturing process was complete, a new mathematical model could be constructed to predict the behaviour of the manufactured tied-arch. A review of the assumptions required by the

original mathematical model led to changes and additions to this model. These are shown in Figure 12(b), with the theoretical model shown in (a) for comparison:

Figure 12: (a) the original tied arch mechanism (b) the modified tied arch mechanism

The additions accounted for the weight of the structure and the work done in the hinges. Each rigid link was assumed to have a mass, m , acting at its centre, and each hinge was assumed to require a slip-stick moment, M_p , to overcome its friction. These components are clearly shown in the modified equation for the total potential energy of the system:

$$\text{Original Total potential energy of system, } V = U - PE_p$$

$$\text{Modified Total potential energy of system, } V = U - PE_p - 2mgE_w - W_H$$

Equation 8

The displacement of the self-weight, E_w , and the work done in the hinges, W_H , are defined below:

$$\text{Downwards displacement of self - weight, } E_w = \frac{L}{2}(\sin \alpha - \sin Q_1)$$

Equation 9

$$\text{Work done in hinges during first downwards stroke, } W_H = 4M_p(\alpha - Q_1)$$

Equation 10

Furthermore, in the modified mechanism, the spring was not mounted at the ends of the planks, but along the length of the planks. This was accounted for by changing the strain energy in the spring:

$$\text{Original strain energy in spring, } U = 2kL^2(\cos Q_1 - \cos \alpha)^2$$

$$\text{Modified strain energy in the spring, } U = 2kL_s^2(\cos Q_1 - \cos \alpha)^2$$

Equation 11

The new constants are shown in Figure 12, above.

These changes led to a modified expression for the dead load at equilibrium:

$$\text{Dead Load at equilibrium, } P = \frac{4kL_s^2(\cos Q_1 - \cos \alpha) \tan Q_1}{L} - mg \pm \frac{4M_p}{L \cos Q_1}$$

Equation 12

The final term is positive for the downwards stroke, and negative for the upwards stroke. This equation gives a revised equilibrium path for the manufactured tied-arch, which could be used to assess how closely the prototype imitates the theoretical mechanism.

4.5 Testing the tied arch

The tied arch prototype responded well when tested qualitatively by applying a force by hand, as would be done in a lecture. Three things should be noted from this test:

- The arch snapped through violently. To avoid this in future models, the self-weight of the arch should be reduced. This is detailed further on p.22.
- By touch, the springs did not appear to be as stiff in compression as in tension.
- A better way to support the arch during demonstrations is needed. The support given by the four studs used when testing the arch in the Instron machine also provides limited stability for demonstrations, but a dramatic improvement could be achieved using the suggestion on p.22.

The tied arch was tested qualitatively using the Instron machine. It was found that the test was repeatable, as successive tests gave very similar results. A typical result is given in Figure 13(a):

Figure 13: (a) a test on the tied arch prototype (blue represents the downwards stroke, and red the upwards stroke); (b) the same test result, edited slightly (green represents extension of the springs, and purple represents compression of the springs)

The labelling in Figure 13(a) shows how the prototype's behaviour corresponds to that predicted in Figure 2, and it shows that the behaviour of the prototype was very similar to that predicted. This result shows that the arch's self-weight has a large effect on its behaviour. The equilibrium compressive load is constantly approximately 13N less than that expected in the theoretical model with no mass. Only a section of the predicted curve has been tested, because of the geometric limitations of the prototype tied arch model, but this is sufficient to convey the teaching points.

Figure 13(b) is a slightly edited version of the original test result. Here, colours are used to distinguish between the compression and extension of the springs. It is clear that two different equilibrium paths

were adopted by the arch during the test, and these appear to correspond to the direction of movement of the spring's coils.

However, it was noted by sight that the arch was horizontal at a compressive displacement of approximately 313mm. Therefore, the change from extension of the springs on the first part of the downward stroke to compression of the springs must have occurred at a value just less than 313mm, because the springs were not mounted on the line between the travelling rods and the central hinge rod, but slightly above it. This can be reconciled with the plot in (b), where the transition point is shown to be between 265mm and 300mm. This supports the conjecture that the different equilibrium paths correspond to the direction of movement of the spring's coils.

The curve shapes shown in (b) are very good approximations to those predicted, however the data cannot be easily fit to the modified theoretical model. Therefore, besides the discrepancies from the theoretical mechanism caused by the prototype's self-weight and the behaviour of the springs in extension and compression, the results fit the theoretical model very well. Therefore, the prototype has imitated the theoretical model accurately, though not as precisely as possible. Suggestions for modifications which could be made to the prototype to improve its behaviour are given below.

4.6 Conclusions

The tied arch prototype has been shown to behave very similarly to the theoretical mechanism on which it is based. Therefore this prototype has satisfied the desired qualitative criteria. Therefore, the prototype is very suitable for demonstrating some of the generic properties of elastic stability theory, and for demonstrating the behaviour of the tied arch mechanism. In particular, the snap-through shown by the tied arch is visually very effective, and provides sufficient motivation to students to ensure that their future design work is not susceptible to such behaviour.

4.7 Further work

The spring mechanism

It was mentioned in the section titled '4.4 Design and Manufacturing considerations', that a possible improvement could be made to the chosen spring mechanism, using an earlier design. A cross-section of the earlier cylindrical design, constructed from aluminium, is shown in Figure 14:

Figure 14: A cross-section of the original design for the spring mechanism, shown in its neutral position

In this design, there are two springs, one extension spring and one compression spring (of larger diameter). These sit inside two cylindrical casings (A and B), which can slide in and out of each other. This movement is resisted in both directions by the springs. The component is shown here in its neutral position, with both springs at their free length and therefore exerting no force.

When the casings move apart from the neutral position (as shown by the dashed lines), the extension spring exerts a force pulling them together. The extension spring is held securely onto each casing by a grub screw, ensuring that its force is transferred to the casings. However, the compression spring must not exert any force when the casings move apart. This is achieved by not attaching it to casing A. A danger is that it should fall down, interfering with the extension spring. This is prevented by the support given by casing A, and if necessary additional support could be introduced into casing B.

When the casings move towards each other from the neutral position, the compression spring exerts a force pushing them apart. X represents a link, where a length of nylon cord has been tied to a loop at the end of the extension spring's wire. The line to the left of X is the nylon cord, whereas to the right is wire. This prevents the extension spring from interfering with this motion, as the cord cannot carry compressive forces.

Finally, the design includes consideration as to how the mechanism would be manufactured and put together. Casing A differs from casing B in that the hole for the cord to be threaded through passes from the interior of the casing through to the exterior. This is important because without it the mechanism would be nearly impossible to put together.

This earlier design would directly replace the design used in the prototypes. It fits on the same rods, held in place by imperfectionators on the planks. It has two major disadvantages. Firstly, the springs cannot be seen moving due to the casing around them: even if the casing was made from transparent material, it would still be hard for an audience to distinguish the separate springs and parts moving in the mechanism. Secondly, this design is much more complex than the design used in the prototypes. This has several unfavourable consequences:

- It is harder to explain how it works briefly in a lecture.
- The manufacturing process requires much more time, and is considerably more expensive.

- The mass of the original mechanism is much greater than that of the prototypes, which would move the prototype further from the original theoretical assumption of no mass.
- The mechanism is slightly difficult to put together.

Reducing the tied arch's mass

There are two easy ways to reduce the mass of the tied arch, and bring it closer to the theoretical model's specification.

Firstly, the mass of the planks could be reduced. When manufacturing prototypes, it was important to use planks for the rigid links, so that the imperfectionators could be positioned anywhere along the width and length of the plank by drilling extra holes whilst trialling, and so that the planks could be easily seen in a lecture. However, now that a final design has been found, the planks are over-engineered for their requirements. Instead, large chunks could be cut out from the planks to reduce their mass, whilst keeping enough strength and ensuring that holes could be drilled where necessary to secure the imperfectionators. To maintain the visual impact of the planks, a plank of MDF (or similar) of minimal thickness (say 3mm) could be overlaid on this now much reduced plank.

Secondly, the brass hinge offers the biggest potential reduction in mass. It should be replaced by two imperfectionators on each plank and a rod passing through these two sets of imperfectionators. This would achieve the same hinge action whilst reducing the mass significantly. This has many additional advantages. Firstly, imperfectionators give less compliance in the hinge, as they can be placed further apart along the length of the hinge rod. Secondly, they allow for a greater angle of movement of the arch, as the planks can be placed further apart (using modified, longer imperfectionators). Furthermore, the only reason that a brass hinge was thought to be advantageous was its visual impact, but a hinge made using imperfectionators would be just as easy to understand at a glance.

Adapting the rig for demonstration purposes

It has already been noted (on p.11) that the arch will have to be clamped at one end when being used for demonstration purposes. At present, the other travelling rod which is free to move will collide with the supporting studs when the arch reaches certain positions. To avoid this, it is recommended that additional Ø18 holes be drilled for the studs at the corners of the frame for use in lectures, replacing the current Ø6 holes used to bolt the frame together at the corners. They would house studs which would now hold the frame together as well as supporting it, and the travelling rods would no longer collide with the studs.

5. An Investigation into the Buckling Behaviour of Arches

5.1 Overview

The aims of this investigation were:

- To investigate how the critical load applied to an arch varies with the eccentricity of the force application along the strip's length.
- To investigate the behaviour of the test rig, which it was hoped would be used in further experiments to test the behaviour of spring and rod mechanisms.
- To provide an outline of how arches buckle, and to give an insight into the experiments performed by John Roorda (Roorda, 1965).

To satisfy these aims, the following experiments were conducted:

- Tests on arches made from mild steel strips of different dimensions to determine the most appropriate size of strip on which to conduct further tests.
- An initial test on the chosen strip with a point load applied at a variety of offsets from the geometric centre of the length of the strip, to determine the range of offsets which should be investigated in further detail.
- A series of tests on the chosen strip over the chosen range of offsets.

5.2 Previous Research

The context to this investigation is given by three sources (although many others have contributed to the understanding of the buckling beams and struts). These are (Thompson & Hunt, 1984), (Bazant & Cedolin, 2003) and (Roorda, 1965). The former deals “with the buckling and post-buckling of engineering structures and components”¹⁶, from which many results are quoted. Bazant and Cedolin provide a basis for the 5.3 Theoretical and Experimental Buckling section below. Roorda's paper summarises experiments carried out to investigate the stability of structures with small imperfections. This gave inspiration for the setup of the experiment and some experimental data for comparison.

5.3 Theoretical and Experimental Buckling

There are two types of buckling analysis which are useful for predicting the buckling of metal strips. These are:

¹⁶ (Thompson & Hunt, 1984), blurb

- Buckling of high arches: “High arches are those for which the centre line of the arch may be considered incompressible.”¹⁷ High arches are sensitive to manufacturing imperfections; hence the maximum load that they can sustain reduces dramatically as imperfection size increases.
- Buckling of flat arches: “Flat (or shallow) arches are those for which its [the centre line’s] shortening is important.”¹⁸ They “may be assumed to fail in a symmetric mode.”¹⁹ Flat arches only have weak imperfection sensitivity to small offset loads, so manufacturing imperfections are not the concern that they are for high arches.

The test conditions that Roorda used to test a buckled steel strip were imitated with the hope of repeating the experiments. Roorda wrote that he tested a “shallow” arch, although the theory used to analyse the results was that of high arches. The strips used in Roorda’s and the new experiments were so slender (the new slenderness ratio ≈ 700), and the forces applied so small (usually less than 20N), that it was thought that the shortening of the centre line would be negligible. Analysis of the results showed that the strips used acted as high arches.

Buckling analysis of high arches

The analysis of circular arches with a point load applied at their centre given by (Bazant & Cedolin)²⁰ is particularly relevant to the buckling of high arches. This analysis is summarised in Figure 15:

IMAGE REDACTED FOR COPYRIGHT PURPOSES

Figure 15: The buckling modes for a circular arch under a point load with pinned joints, and their interaction.²¹

Figure 15 suggests that perfect pinned circular arches will deflect in their symmetric mode initially, as shown in (a). At a critical point they will snap into their asymmetric mode, as this becomes the mode with a lower equilibrium load, shown in (c). However, “slender arches ... are imperfection sensitive”²². These imperfections introduce the asymmetric mode as a transitional state between the two original modes. The new equilibrium path is shown in (d) by the plot labelled ‘ $e \neq 0$ ’, and is due to the new asymmetric mode brought about by the asymmetry of the system. Figure 16 shows how the buckling load at the critical point for a metal strip varied with the load’s offset in Roorda’s experiments. It was expected that results from similar experiments conducted on the metal strips

¹⁷ (Bazant & Cedolin), p.108

¹⁸ (Bazant & Cedolin), p.108

¹⁹ (Bazant & Cedolin), p.231

²⁰ (Bazant & Cedolin), p.112

²¹ Copied from (Bazant & Cedolin), p.113, with the Antisymmetric mode added.

²² (Bazant & Cedolin), p.113

would take the form of this curve for loads offset from the strip’s centre. Furthermore, as this offset increases, the maximum load will decrease as shown by Roorda’s experimental results in Figure 16:

IMAGE REDACTED FOR COPYRIGHT PURPOSES

Figure 16: Roorda’s results of the buckling loads for a steel strip, loaded at various offsets.²³ P = maximum load, P_{crit} = maximum theoretical load, f = offset, f₀ = offset of buckling centre from geometric centre, L = span, h = rise.

The theoretical curve, as given later in Equation 13 (p.32), is a two-thirds power law, as is the general case for asymmetric bifurcations. Roorda does not attempt to compare his results to theory, but for reference the theory gives the same shape of curve as the curve fitted to his data. Both the conclusions about the mode shapes adopted during buckling and the imperfection sensitivity of the steel strips are supported by Saunders’ analysis of the pinned Euler strut.²⁴

5.4 Design and Manufacturing considerations

The steel strips

Roorda tested the buckling loads of “a shallow arch formed by buckling a straight 1in. by 1/16in. steel strip into an approximately sinusoidal curve with a span of 24in. and a rise of 1.50in.”²⁵ The rig used for the tied arch was to be used to test the steel strips too, fixing the span of the arch, and giving two selection criteria with which to choose the dimensions of an appropriate steel strip:

- The cross-section of the new strip (taken perpendicularly to its length) would be the same as that used by Roorda, to ensure that the new strip had the same stiffness.
- The new strip would have a larger span and rise than Roorda’s strip. The ratio of the new span to the new rise would be the approximately equal to that of Roorda’s strip.

The chosen dimensions are shown for the ‘new’ experiment in Table 2 alongside the original dimensions used by Roorda:

Experiment	Material	Width / mm	Depth / mm	Length / mm	Span / mm	Rise / mm
Roorda	Steel	25.4	1.59	unknown	610	38.1
New	Mild Steel	25	1.6	1116	1092	69.0

Table 2: A comparison of the properties of the strips used to form an arch by Roorda and in the current experiments.

²³ Modified from (Roorda, 1965), p.104

²⁴ (Saunders, 1980), p.76-8

²⁵ (Roorda, 1965), p.102

In the new experiment, problems were encountered with the yielding of the strips. It appears that no such problems were encountered by Roorda. Therefore, in hindsight it appears that Roorda probably used high-grade steel (with a much larger yield stress than mild steel), and this would have been more appropriate for the new experiment.

The rig

Three modifications were made to the setup used for the tied arch experiments. The first was to attach MDF pieces inside the rig, as shown in Figure 17. This stopped the strips from splitting the timber frame, and provided a slot in which the strip ends could rotate in the same fashion as pinned joints.

Figure 17: The layout of the MDF pieces fixed to the insides of the crossbeams

The strip slotted between the MDF pieces and through the crosshead fixing as shown in Figure 18:

Figure 18: The setup used to test a steel strip

The second modification, shown in Figure 18, was to add a rod to the manufactured fixing to fix the strip to the crosshead, as mentioned previously. This new fixing allowed upwards and downwards forces to be applied to the strip, and gave enough room for the strip to bend as necessary. At this stage, the rig could be used to investigate the behaviour of the strips under a central load. However, there was no way to apply the force at a position offset from the centre of the strip. To do so, the rig had to move because the crosshead fixing was unable to move horizontally. Therefore, the third modification (shown in Figure 18) was to replace the side pieces of the frame with new, simpler pieces to allow the rig to be moved horizontally. These could replace the originals in all contexts.

The new side pieces are wider than the originals, and are of constant width throughout, to provide the required additional strength. The studs supporting the frame could be positioned at any point along the

length of the slots running along the centres of the strips. This allowed the frame to be fixed with the crosshead fixing now positioned at an offset to the geometric centre of the strip.

5.5 Preliminary tests on strips of different dimensions

Initially, tests were conducted on mild steel strips of different dimensions to ensure that the dimensions chosen in the design considerations gave a strip which did not significantly deform plastically. The strips' dimensions were chosen to give a range of rise values. In addition, a strip of a different width and depth were tested. The strip dimensions were (in mm):

Strip A: 1116 x 25 x 1.6 Strip B: 1136 x 25 x 1.6 Strip C: 1156 x 25 x 1.6

Strip D: 1116 x 30 x 1.6 Strip E: 1116 x 25 x 1.0

Strip E, which was considerably more slender than the others, deformed plastically to such an extent that the test had to be stopped. The other results are given in Figure 19:

Figure 19: Load versus displacement plots for the strips. (Blue shows the initial downward stroke, red shows the following upward stroke)

These graphs give important insight into the buckling of the strips. Strips A to C had adopted the asymmetric mode shape at their critical compressive load (P_{crit} , the load at a maximum on the blue curves). In contrast, strip D adopted the symmetric mode shape initially. It continued in this mode shape until well after reaching P_{crit} . It then snapped into the asymmetric mode shape that the other three strips had used throughout (see Figure 15 for an explanation of the mode shapes). The

symmetric mode shape has a greater curvature than the asymmetric mode shape for a given displacement. Therefore the strain energy which this mode shape absorbs whilst deflecting is higher, leading to a significantly greater P_{crit} value.

It is unclear whether a designer could ensure that the higher order mode shape was adopted until P_{crit} , giving a much higher value of P_{crit} and a more efficient design. The following tests which apply a point load at different offsets from the centre of the length of the beam should help to determine this.

When applying a force to the strips, there is a danger of plastically deforming the strips, dissipating energy as heat. This is to be avoided because it introduces an extra unknown into the tests, and because the theory used to predict the strips' behaviour relies on the strips behaving elastically.

Figure 20: The strips after testing.

After testing, Strips B, C and D had undergone plastic deformation, as shown by their visible deformation in Figure 20. The energy dissipated during each test cycle was found from the graphs in Figure 19 by integrating the area in the hysteresis loop, and is given in Table 3. This energy loss could be due to many mechanisms including: plastic deformation, friction between the strip and the frame, and friction between the crevice rods and the strip. Therefore, the proportion of the energy dissipated may show dissipation processes other than plastic deformation. However, small changes in the dimensions of the strip are unlikely to affect the amount of energy dissipated through other dissipation processes. Consequently, large discrepancies between strips of the proportion of input energy dissipated are likely to indicate plastic deformation.

Strip name	Energy dissipated / mJ (3sf)	Proportion of input energy dissipated / % (3sf)
Strip A	38.0	1.80
Strip B	122	4.42
Strip C	271	9.93
Strip D ²⁶	908	27.0

Table 3: The energy losses in initial tests on strips of different dimensions

As there was no visible plastic deformation on strip A, and it had an acceptably low proportion of input energy dissipated during the test, it was used for all subsequent tests.

²⁶ The large energy losses in Strip D were largely due to the change of mode shape on the downwards sweep, dissipating energy in vibrations of the strip. For this reason, the value of energy loss given is not comparable with the others. However, the strip's plastic deformation is clearly seen in Figure 20.

5.6 Preliminary tests to determine the suitable range of eccentricities

These tests were used to determine the range of eccentricities over which the steel strip should be tested. A wide range of offsets of the point load were chosen to be tested. It was expected that the geometric centre of the strip would coincide approximately with the centre of this range. A plot of the critical loads at each of the (arbitrary) offsets is given in Figure 21:

Figure 21: A graph of critical loads for a wide range of eccentricities

This graph shows that the critical load required to deflect the strip does indeed decrease with distance from the centre of the strip. It also suggests that a suitable range of eccentricities would span approximately 30mm, as shown. Therefore, a range of 36mm was chosen, 18mm either side of the geometric centre of the strip. Tests would be conducted at 3mm intervals along this 36mm range, to give at least six values with which to plot a curve on either side of the geometric centre.

However, in retrospect the above conclusions were based on unreliable data. The critical loads used in Figure 21 were all found with the strip in the asymmetric mode shape, with the exception of the values at 60mm and 70mm offsets, which adopted the symmetric mode shape initially. The importance of the mode shapes in which the critical load was measured is detailed on p.30.

5.7 Preliminary Tests to determine the compressive displacement required

These preliminary tests were used to determine the compressive displacement required to achieve accurate measurements of the critical load. At least 52 tests were to be carried out, so a reduction of the compressive displacement would considerably reduce the testing time.

Tests of compressive displacement ranges of 40mm and 100mm were performed to investigate whether there was any advantage in running the test over a greater displacement. There was no discernible difference between the results produced over the first 40mm compressive displacement between the two lengths of tests. Therefore, a compressive displacement of 40mm was used to save time when testing. Antisymmetric mode shapes would never be encountered with this displacement.

5.8 Tests to investigate the effect of applying the force at an offset

It was decided that four tests would be conducted at each offset value, one for each orientation of the strip. This gave four separate sets of results, which could not be easily combined because the buckling centre of the strip in each orientation would be different. (The buckling centre is at the offset at which the maximum critical load is encountered, and is slightly different to the geometric centre due to imperfections). Furthermore, when an ‘interesting’ result was encountered, that test was repeated. Figure 22 shows the results of three repeats of a particular orientation of the strip:

Figure 22: Three plots of repeat tests on the strip at an offset value of -3mm

The results of the three tests are very different, although all testing conditions were the same. This shows that the results are subject to large variations for no predictable reason. The variation in the results can be understood by considering the behaviour of the strip in each of the tests.

In the test conducted to give (b), the strip entered an asymmetric mode immediately after the load came into contact with the strip. It remained in this mode throughout the test. (c), on the other hand, shows a test in which the strip remained in a symmetric mode until over half-way through the upwards stroke. At this point, an asymmetric mode shape was adopted, and the excess strain energy in the strip was dissipated in its vibration upon adopting this new shape. The critical load was far greater than in (b) because of the mode shape. Similarly, in the test shown in (a), a symmetric mode shape was adopted at first, followed by an asymmetric shape. However, the transition occurred much sooner, on the downwards stroke rather than the upwards stroke, and therefore the critical load was lower than in (c). The transition occurred after the critical load for an asymmetric mode shape was passed, but before the critical load for a symmetric mode shape, therefore the critical load was between the two. The variation in results is caused by variation in the mode shapes adopted during the tests, and the stages at which they are adopted, as supported by the results throughout the tests. Two repeats of a test were taken, during which the same mode shapes were adopted at the same stages during the tests.

Figure 23: (a) the results of the first repeat of a test with an offset of +12mm (b) the results of the second repeat

Figure 23 shows that the two sets of results are strikingly similar. In each test the strip changed from a symmetric mode shape initially, to an asymmetric mode shape, and in both instances this was just before 10mm compressive displacement, which was before the critical load for the asymmetric mode shape was reached. Therefore, the critical load in each was determined by the asymmetric mode shape. The two critical loads were 6.54N and 6.49N respectively, a difference of less than 1%.

The large vibration in Figure 22(c) shows visually the transfer of energy from strain energy to being dissipated during a change from a higher-energy mode shape (symmetric) to a lower-energy mode shape (asymmetric). The proportion of the input energy dissipated during the tests gives useful insight into the mode shapes adopted in the tests. In the tests in Figure 22, the proportions are (a) 0.9350, (b) 0.9537, (c) 0.9249. This is a wide range, reflecting the variation in behaviour during the tests. In contrast, in the tests in Figure 23, the proportions are (a) 0.9645, (b) 0.9668. These cover a much smaller range because the behaviour in the tests was so similar. This gives physical reasoning to the question of why the critical loads can vary so dramatically in repeat tests.

Some background has been given of the behaviour of the strip. Now the analysis is presented for the entire range of results. Only the results from one of the four orientations gave a clear trend to which a curve could be fitted. These results are shown (including repeated tests) in Figure 24:

Figure 24: The results from one particular orientation (including repeated tests)

The analysis of these results relies on filtering out the unreliable results, in order to see the trend clearly and to fit a curve to the most appropriate points. Because of the importance of the mode shapes

at which these critical loads were found, this criterion has been used to distinguish the reliable from the unreliable points. Those points which represent tests in which the critical load occurred in a symmetric mode shape are considered unreliable, unless they occurred at small offsets, in which case they were considered reliable because these offsets are where you would expect the symmetric mode shape to be adopted. This is summarised in the following key:

- Key: + point produced by an asymmetric mode shape (and therefore reliable)
 × point produced by a symmetric mode shape at a small offset (and therefore reliable)
 × point produced by a symmetric mode shape at a large offset (and therefore unreliable)

For five of the six closest points to the buckling centre of the strip (an offset of approximately -3.2mm, as explained below) the critical load occurred in the symmetric mode shape. In contrast, for three of the remaining twelve points further from the buckling centre, the critical load occurred in the asymmetric mode. This, admittedly weakly, supports the argument presented above. It would be unreasonable to expect stronger statistical support, within the time constraints, as over 120 tests were conducted in total for the three investigations in this project over a period of weeks.

Thomson and Hunt²⁷ state that for an “arch formed from an initially straight strut”, the ratio of the critical load (P) at an offset (ϵL ; L= strip length) to the critical load at zero offset (P_C) is given by (a):

$$(a) \frac{P}{P_C} = 1 - 3.22\epsilon^{\frac{2}{3}} \quad (b) P = P_C - a|\epsilon - \epsilon_0|^c$$

Equation 13(a) and (b)

(a) is rearranged to a more general form in (b), where a and c are constants, and $\epsilon_0 L$ is the offset from the geometric centre at the buckling centre.

The imperfection sensitivity given here as a two-thirds power law is characteristic of an unstable symmetric bifurcation, showing that this theory relies on a symmetric mode being adopted at the critical load. Therefore, this theory predicts the imperfection sensitivity for arches buckling under the maximum critical load for a symmetric mode. This only happened twice in the 63 successful tests carried out on the strip. If the tests were to be continued, a method of ensuring that the strip adopted a symmetric mode shape, and remained in that mode shape until the critical load was reached, would be needed. One of the two tests in which this occurred is shown in Figure 22(c) (p.30). An important feature of this test is that the curve showing the downwards stroke (shown in red) reaches a maximum. This shows that the maximum critical load for that mode shape, at that offset, has been reached (within experimental error). This is the same point with a critical load of 14.04N as in Figure 24. It is clear that adopting the symmetric mode shape is not enough to make a point accurate, but it must also

²⁷ (Thompson & Hunt, Elastic Instability Phenomena, 1984), p.105

stay in this mode shape until a maximum load is passed. Therefore, only two results were accurate out of the 63 tests on this strip. The second had a very comparable critical load of 14.22N.

Two approaches were used to fit a curve to the points which were considered reliable above. For both, the generalised Equation 13(b) was used. Acknowledgements to Paul Taylor for fitting a curve by finding the optimal values of each of the four constants in Equation 13(b). Two results of the curve fitting are shown in Figure 25:

Figure 25: The curves fitted to the reliable data points: (a) assumes a critical load of 15N at zero offset; (b) assumes a critical load of 30N at zero offset.

The curves shown here are not symmetric (as the theory suggests they should be), but have been fitted for each half of the data individually. The data was split at the estimated buckling centre of -3.2mm offset (giving $\varepsilon_0 L = 0.0029$). For the first 5mm either side of this new centre, the curve has been reflected from the opposite side to compare how close to the two curves are to being symmetrical. (a) assumes a critical load at zero offset of 15N. (b) assumes a critical load at zero offset of 30N. (a) is more symmetrical than (b), although both are very close to being symmetrical, giving the data extra validity. There is little difference in how well the two sets of curves fit the data points, and therefore a critical load of approximately 15N was preferred. However, when the data set was considered as a whole and a symmetrical curve was fit to the set, the closest fit was found to be given by:

$$P \approx 33.5 - 21.8|\varepsilon + 0.0029|^{0.077}$$

Equation 14

In this equation, the eccentricity is to the power of 0.077, rather than 0.67 as expected. This discrepancy may be explained by the use of data obtained by both symmetric and asymmetric mode shapes. Furthermore, the range of offsets used here is far greater than that used by Roorda (over 20 times greater). It is not clear whether the theory remains applicable over such large offsets.

A second analysis is given of only the data set with a positive offset from the buckling centre. This analysis was based on the expected values of the constants, leaving 'c' to be determined by the curve with the best fit. An additional point was used, which was that at $P = P_C$, $\varepsilon = \varepsilon_0$. P_C was set at 17N, slightly above that of the two data points which passed a critical load in the symmetric buckling mode.

ε_0 was set at -3.9mm because this was the centre of the two sides of data found by hand. When ‘a’ was set to approximately $3.22P_C$, as predicted by theory, the value of ‘c’ which gave the best-fit curve was 0.373. The curve is shown in Figure 27:

Figure 26: A best-fit curve fit to the data with a positive offset from the buckling centre.

This approach gives a reasonable fit, just as the previous approach did. It uses constants which are much closer to the theoretical values, as shown by the comparison of the theoretical curve and this experimental curve in Equation 15 (a) and (b). (c) is the optimal curve given for comparison.

$$(a) P = P_C - 3.22P_C|\varepsilon - \varepsilon_0|^{\frac{2}{3}} \qquad (b) P \approx 17 - 3.22 \times 17|\varepsilon + 0.0035|^{0.37}$$

$$(c) P \approx 33.5 - 0.66 \times 33.5|\varepsilon + 0.0029|^{0.08}$$

Equation 15: (a) the theoretical equation for an initially straight strut buckled into a high arch; (b) an experimental equation found by setting all values apart from the power; (c) an experimental equation found by setting all values using an optimal curve fit.

(b) and (c) show that there is a wide range of curves which could fit the data. With the available data, it is not possible to determine which is the most appropriate.

5.9 Conclusions

The qualitative behaviour of the strips was very similar to that of both the tied arch mechanism and prototype model. This strongly supports the argument in favour of using elastic stability theory and the prototypes to give students an understanding of the effects of imperfections in structural design. However, the strips’ quantitative behaviour could not be accurately deduced with the available data.

5.10 Further work

To imitate Roorda’s experiments more closely, a narrower range of offsets, high grade steel strips, and a method of ensuring that the strips adopted the symmetric mode shape at all times would be needed. Roorda probably also used strips of a higher rise, and joints at the strip’s ends of much less friction, so it would be beneficial to incorporate these. Finally, a more stable rig would be required to ensure accurate offsets were measured.

6. The Spring and Link Model

6.1 Overview

The second mechanism to be imitated is a ‘spring and link model’, shown in its post-buckling state in Figure 27(a). This model is useful for analysing the response of a flat plate to an axial load.

Figure 27: (a) theoretical spring and link mechanism in its post-buckling state²⁸, used to approximate the behaviour of: (b) an axially-loaded plate (also shown here in its post-buckling state).

A full derivation of many aspects of the mechanism’s behaviour is given by Thomson and Hunt²⁹.

It is important to explain the terminology used in the explanation of the model. Note the co-ordinate system shown in Figure 27(a). The term ‘x-springs’ refers to springs which lie parallel to the x-axis. Similarly, the term ‘z-springs’ refers to springs which lie parallel to the z-axis. Therefore, in Figure 27, the x-springs are those with stiffness of k_2 , and the only z-spring has stiffness k_1 .

There are four key components of the mechanism’s behaviour:

1. Initially the axial load, P , results in pure squash of the x-springs, producing end-shortening (of displacement $Q_2 L$), whilst $q_1 = 0$. This pre-buckling response is linear with respect to Q_2 and is given by:

$$P = 3k_2 L Q_2 \quad \text{for } q_1 = 0$$

Equation 16

2. This response becomes unstable at a critical point of symmetric bifurcation. The critical load at this point is given by:

$$P_{crit} = \frac{3k_1 L}{2} \quad \text{for } Q_2 = Q_{2c}$$

Equation 17

²⁸ Adapted from a figure in (Thompson & Hunt, 1984), p.78; acknowledgements to (Taylor, 2009), lecture 8, p.1
²⁹ (Thompson & Hunt, 1984), pp.77-83; many of the ideas in this section are taken from this source.

- The central links of length L may deflect in either the positive or the negative z -direction at this critical point, compressing or extending the z -spring. This sheds load from the central x -spring to the z -spring. The gradient of this linear post-buckling response is given by Equation 18. The response can be stable (positive gradient) or unstable (negative gradient), and continues until Q_2 has increased from its value at the critical point by $4/3$.

$$\frac{dP}{dQ_2} = k_2 L \frac{8k_2 - 3k_1}{4k_2 - k_1} \quad \text{for } Q_{2c} < Q_2 < \left(Q_{2c} + \frac{4}{3}\right)$$

Equation 18

Therefore, the stability of this section of the equilibrium path is determined by the ratio of k_1 to k_2 . The transition between stable and unstable bifurcation occurs at $3k_1=8k_2$. For ratios of k_1/k_2 greater than this, the post-buckling path is unstable.

- When buckling is complete, the response follows a third, stable equilibrium path of the same gradient as the initial path.

The complete response is shown in Figure 28. Two paths are illustrated for the post-buckling response, generated using different ratios of spring stiffnesses.

Figure 28: The force-displacement response of the spring and link model³⁰

6.2 Relevance

The behaviour of this mechanism resembles the behaviour of an axially-loaded flat plate. In the Q_2 direction, the pre-buckling response (when $q_1 \approx 0$, so the hinge remains in the x - y plane) and the initial post-buckling response ($|q_1| > 0$, and hinge moves out of the x - y plane) both resemble the responses

³⁰ Adapted from a figure in (Thompson & Hunt, 1984), p.82; acknowledgements to (Taylor, 2009), lecture 8, p.6

given by an axially-loaded plate. The mechanism's axial length reduces under load (by Q_2L), just as a flat plate would. In addition, the mechanism buckles in the z- direction at a critical load, so the mechanism shows the visual deformation of a flat plate. This comparison is shown in Figure 27(b).

There are two important lessons which this mechanism can help to teach structural engineers:

- The first lesson is the possibility that a plate undergoes a dynamic snap. A dynamic snap is when the strain does not have a fixed value, but can increase instantaneously under constant stress. When designing plates, this mechanism shows that a plate's dimensions could be naively optimised to increase its failure strength, but that this optimisation would allow the plate to undergo dynamic snaps, giving destructive behaviour. This is shown by the unstable equilibrium paths given by higher values of k_1/k_2 . It appears to be desirable to increase the value of k_1 to increase the critical load at which buckling occurs (given by Equation 17), and therefore increase its failure strength. However, this will also decrease the stability of the post-buckling path, as it is determined by k_1/k_2 . When subjected to a dead load, failure will be catastrophic for unstable paths. The system will undergo dynamic jumps if $k_1 > 4k_2$ (as shown in Figure 28). This dramatic behaviour is to be avoided in most contexts.
- Secondly, the mechanism's theoretical behaviour does not accurately model the behaviour of a manufactured flat plate, as it does not account for imperfections. However, the model does demonstrate the effect of imperfections as its imperfection-sensitivity is given by a $2/3$ power law. The maximum pre-buckling load (and failure strength) when an imperfection is introduced into the model is given by P in Equation 19:

$$\frac{P}{P_c} = 1 - c\varepsilon^{2/3}$$

Equation 19³¹

For example, an imperfection in a flat plate could be represented in this model by a spring being initially too long by ε . This gives a dramatic reduction in failure strength with increasing imperfection size. This problem could not be shown using the tied arch mechanism.

6.3 Design criteria

When realising this mechanism physically, it was hoped that the following behavioural characteristics could be shown:

- Pre-buckling, initial axial movement of the point of load application compresses only the x-springs.
- Post-buckling, the central links move in the z-direction compressing the z-spring, whilst the x-springs continue to be compressed.

³¹ (Thompson & Hunt, Elastic Instability Phenomena, 1984), p.105

- Further axial movement of the point of load application after the completion of buckling gives compression of the x-springs only.

Furthermore, it was hoped that the prototype would closely resemble the mechanism, so that the two would be easily visually comparable. Accurate quantitative behaviour of the model was not a requirement. The following idealised aspects of the model's behaviour could be used as a golden standard to assess how closely the prototype imitated the theoretical mechanism:

- A linear force-displacement pre-buckling response (shown by the green path in Figure 28).
- Bifurcation of the equilibrium path at the critical point, as shown by q_1 being able to take both positive and negative values. Ideally, the bifurcation could be easily altered between stable symmetric and unstable symmetric. This would allow the lecturer to demonstrate both the undesirable behaviour given by a poorly-designed unstable system, and the much improved behaviour of a stable system.
- A second linear response as load shedding occurs, post-buckling (shown in black paths in Figure 28). (During this response, load is shed from the x-springs to the z-spring.)
- A third linear response, after buckling has completed, with the same gradient as the initial pre-buckling response (shown in blue in Figure 28).

6.4 Design and Manufacturing considerations

Equal compression of x-springs

The x-springs must all undergo the same displacements for the theoretical behaviour to be satisfied. Consequently, the travelling rod (shown in bold in Figure 27(a)) must remain parallel to the y-axis at all displacements, with no rotation about the z-axis. In practice, to reduce rotation about the z-axis, the following measures were taken:

- The central x-spring and the z-spring were each replaced by two parallel springs. The replacement springs each had half of the stiffness of the original springs, to give the same total stiffness.
- The central links were replaced by stiff plates.
- The outer x-springs were placed as far apart as possible along the y-axis.
- A moving arm was added between the central x-spring and the central links. This allowed the springs which had replaced the central x-spring to also be separated as far as possible along the y-axis.

Figure 29 shows these adaptations:

Figure 29: A developed version of the spring and link mechanism

This figure omits the details of the fixings of the out-of-plane springs, as these are discussed under the ‘6.5 Design and manufacturing considerations for the z-springs’ section, on p.40.

X-springs

The x-springs, (whose stiffnesses are given in terms of k_2 in Figure 29), have similar requirements to the springs used in the tied arch design. However, they have the additional requirement that some of the clamps used must sit along the length of the travelling rods, rather than at the ends. As the original end-clamps were not able to do this, the mid-clamp was designed. As four end-clamps had already been manufactured for use in the tied arch, these end-clamps were used where possible in the spring and link model to save additional manufacturing, as shown in Figure 29 above.

The remaining design of the x-spring mechanisms was almost the same as the design of those used for the tied arch. The only difference was in the lengths of the springs. The desired relative stiffnesses of the springs were k_2 for the outer springs and $\frac{1}{2} k_2$ for the inner springs. It was difficult to predict the actual stiffnesses of springs bought externally from their catalogued stiffnesses. Therefore, it was decided that the relative stiffnesses could not be achieved by purchasing two sets of springs, one of twice the catalogued stiffness of the other. Instead, the same type of spring was used for all four x-springs. To achieve the different stiffnesses, the outer springs were cut to half the length of the inner springs, allowing the ratio of the stiffness values to be accurately determined.

Finally, the range of movement of the travelling rods (shown in bold in Figure 29) had to be large to allow the central plates to fold together. This required the maximum possible elastic compression of the springs, which was achieved by specifying two spring dimensions. The springs’ free lengths (lengths with no force applied) were to be as great as possible, with their solid lengths (completely

compressed lengths) as small as possible. Therefore, springs were chosen with a free length of 610mm and a solid length of 261mm. Their full length was used for the inner springs, whilst half the length was used for the outer springs, to achieve the required ratio of stiffnesses.

The conclusion that the inner x-springs should be twice the length of the outer x-springs prevented the outer spring mechanisms from simply being attached to the travelling rods because the force produced by the longer outer springs had to span a much larger distance than that of the shorter inner springs. To transmit the outer springs' force over the required distance, the left-over end-clamps were used to clamp the springs rigidly to the rod as shown in Figure 29.

6.5 Design and manufacturing considerations for the z-springs

The z-springs presented the biggest challenge in realising the spring and link model, and therefore require their own section. They can be seen in Figure 29, as part of the whole model, and are shown isolated from the other components in Figure 30(a):

Figure 30: (a) the z-springs (b) the slider concept

The z-springs should satisfy the same criteria as the x-springs, except that they should always act parallel to the z-axis, regardless of the displacements of the other components in the system. To do this the springs must remain parallel to the z-axis, meaning that they must move directly above the hinge joining the stiff plates.

No solution to this problem was found which adequately satisfied the desired criteria. However, four prototypes were manufactured for the z-spring component. These are described in the rest of this section, accompanied by views of each prototype.

The slider prototype

The first solution proposed was based on the visual impression given by Figure 27(a). To produce a component to act in the manner shown in the diagram, a slider was designed and manufactured to fulfil the role. Its design is outlined in Figure 30(b), above.

In the same manner as the fold singularity, each end of the sliding rods ran between two steel plates. These two plates were mounted on the new side pieces for the frame, designed to apply offsets loads to the strips. These side pieces were in turn held parallel to the frame's sides, for which the original

side pieces were used, providing support for the slider. This is shown in Figure 39 (p.47). These plates ensure that the slider cannot rotate about the x- or y-axes, and therefore that the springs act in the z-direction. A slider was designed and manufactured from aluminium bars, incorporating two clamping mechanisms. This is shown in Figure 31:

Figure 31: The slider design

This slider was designed to be manufactured as quickly and as cheaply as possible. Therefore, standard sizes of bars and a simple design were used to avoid excessive machining. Furthermore, the clamps used were designed to be simpler than the other clamps, as only one rod had to pass through them. All the parts were bolted or screwed together.

The holes shown in bold in Figure 31 each hold an internal bar for the z-spring mechanisms. This internal bar continues down to the central hinge where end-clamps fix the bar and spring to the hinge rod (Figure 34 shows the assembled mechanism, p.43). When the slider was used in the spring and link model, frictional forces stopped the rods from moving. The frictional forces developed between the rods and the simplified clamps' casings as shown in the cross-section of a casing in Figure 32:

Figure 32: Forces acting on a stationary rod in one of the slider's clamps. The bold corners of the casing correspond to the bold edge of the holes in Figure 31.

The magnitudes of the frictional forces (F_1 and F_2) are proportional to the reaction forces (R_1 and R_2). The reaction forces must be large enough to move the slider in the x -direction, meaning that the frictional forces incurred must also be relatively large. This appears to be inherent to the design. Three possible ways in which the friction could be reduced are shown in Figure 33, and explained below:

Figure 33: Possible methods of reducing friction in the clamps

Figure 33(a) and (b) show possible changes to the holes in the clamps. In (a), the hole edges have been chamfered, and in (b) the contact area between the rod and the casing has been reduced, which may reduce the friction forces in practice. In (c) the points of contact are coated in acetal, and an acetal rod is used rather than a steel rod. This would reduce the frictional forces significantly, as the co-efficient of friction between two acetal surfaces is much lower than between two steel surfaces.

Whilst manufacturing the slider components, the one measure taken to attempt to reduce the friction is shown in (d). The casing has been left untouched, but the rod has been filed down to give a square rod to reduce the area of contact. This did not produce any noticeable reduction in friction, but this may have been because the flat filed surfaces were much rougher than the original curved surfaces, thereby cancelling any advantage gained by using the square rod. These four measures could be combined to produce the best results, but it is expected that the frictional forces would still be too great.

One advantage of the slider concept over some other designs is that the springs can be initially in tension, compression, or at their free length. This is achieved by moving the metal plates closer to, or further from, the x - y plane, and therefore changing the initial spring length.³² This changes the position of the critical point at which buckling occurs, and in practice determines whether the post-buckling behaviour is stable or unstable. Thus, this method can be used to show the effects of changing the springs' stiffnesses, even though their stiffnesses have not been changed. This is important to demonstrate the importance of stable and unstable behaviour in civil engineering.

Figure 34 (p.43) shows two views of the slider prototype. It shows the prototype in a post-buckling position (note that the design shown in Figure 29 has been rotated to give this prototype). Whilst moving the control rod, the slider had to be supported so that the z -springs pointed perpendicularly to the x - y plane. This allowed the z -spring rods to pass through the slider freely, and therefore allowed the control rod to be displaced. Although the prototype satisfied all the other behavioural criteria, it was not tested quantitatively because it would have been damaged if the control rod was moved without supporting the slider to reduce the frictional forces between the z -spring rods and the slider clamps. For this reason, the prototype could not be used easily in lectures in its current state.

³² In this test the springs were compressed before any displacement was applied to the control rod.

Figure 34: Two views of the slider prototype in a post-buckling position

Therefore, the z-spring mechanism had to be changed, but the remainder of the model's design could remain as it was. Further z-spring designs were manufactured to avoid the frictional forces, as described in the remainder of this section.

The tied-spring prototype

The second design of the z-springs mechanism replaced the slider with a spring between the hinge rod and a fixed point on the x-y plane. This would, in principle, act in the same way as the slider shown in Figure 27(a) if the angle of the spring to the z-axis was kept small enough for the z-springs to be approximately parallel to the z-axis. This is shown for a small angle of fold movement in Figure 35(a):

Figure 35: (a) the tied-spring concept; (b) the modified tied-spring concept (both illustrated for small angles q_1)

Note that in (a) and (b), there are two springs, although one is obscured by the fold. This design is difficult to implement, because the springs have to undergo a very large strain, which is often not possible whilst keeping the springs in the elastic region. One solution is to attach the lower ends of the springs to points significantly below the x-y plane, reducing the strain. This presents two problems:

- If the lower ends of the z-springs were attached to points below the x-y plane it would not be possible to demonstrate the prototype on a flat surface, and clamp the frame to the surface.
- To demonstrate the bifurcation, the fold must be able to buckle in both z-directions. If the springs were mounted below the x-y plane, they would need to be mounted a significant distance from the fold to ensure that the springs' strains remained small enough when the fold deflected below the x-y plane. This would make the prototype significantly more bulky, and less portable.

The concept shown in Figure 35(b) was used to overcome these problems. Here, the spring has been moved to the x-y plane, and an inextensible cord links the spring to the hinge rod. When friction and the extensibility of the cord are ignored, the fold experiences the same force as in (a). The disadvantage of this system is that the layout does not look similar to the original mechanism (Figure 27(a)). However, the priority was to imitate the behaviour of the z-springs in the mechanism, which this concept achieved. The prototype is shown in Figure 36.

Figure 36: (a) rear view of the realised tied-spring prototype (b) front view of the realised tied-spring prototype

Figure 36(a) shows a white nylon cord tied to the hinge rod. The cord was approximately inextensible, and was chosen for its relatively low coefficient of friction. The cord was threaded through a cross-beam, which is the first point of friction (circled). It then passed along the cross-beam, incurring further friction, until it passed through a hole in the cross-beam, the second point of friction (circled). This friction gave sticking points in the cord's movement, and a jerky buckling movement. It also made the process irreversible as the friction stopped the fold from returning to its original position.

Figure 36(b) shows a view from the opposite side of the frame, showing the cord tied onto the spring, allowing the spring's effective length to be adjusted by tying it to any of the coils. The whole prototype is shown in Figure 37:

Figure 37: Two views of the tied-spring prototype, in a post-buckling position

This prototype satisfied most of the desired behavioural characteristics. There was minimal movement of the arch whilst the x-springs were compressed initially, satisfying the first criterion. This was followed by the buckling action, giving the desired extension of the tied z-spring. Like the previous prototype, the arch did not fold completely, allowing the x-springs to be compressed alone afterwards. This is required to satisfy the quantitative criterion that three distinct equilibrium paths are required. However, there was only a small movement of the fold after its post-buckling position, whilst the x-springs were compressed significantly, supporting the user's experience that, qualitatively, the mechanism did satisfy this final criterion.

To improve the behaviour of this model, cams could be mounted at the points where the cord touches the holes' edges for the cord to travel over. These would dramatically reduce the friction at these points, and also lift the cord away from the cross-beam, eliminating the friction along that path. With this adjustment, this mechanism might perform very well.

The fixed-springs prototype

The final attempt made at constructing a component to give the required behaviour of the z-springs was the fixed-springs prototype. This was a development of the tied-spring and slider prototypes. The tied-spring prototype lacked the visual impression of a spring mounted parallel to the z-axis, and the slider prototype showed that the aim of keeping the z-springs parallel to the z-axis may not be achieved within the time constraints of this project. These thoughts gave rise to the fixed-springs prototype, the simplest spring and link prototype yet conceived, shown in Figure 38:

Figure 38: The fixed-springs concept (shown for small angles q_1)

This concept is very similar to the slider mechanism, except that the slider is fixed. The key difference is that the spring rods are free to rotate about the points at which they are fixed to ground, whereas in the slider prototype the slight rotation of the spring rods about the y-axis gave rise to the limiting friction forces. However, this concept does compromise the accuracy of the realised model, because the z-springs are not always parallel to the z-axis. The justification for this is that the z-springs are approximately parallel to the z-axis when the angle, q_1 , is small. The accuracy of this assumption can be improved by increasing the length of the springs, similarly to the tied spring concept.

When manufacturing the fixed-springs component, the beams and metal plates used to support the slider were used to support the fixed-springs. Due to time constraints the points of the springs fixed to ground only rested on one set of bolts between the plates, rather than being fixed between two sets. Therefore, at a certain displacement of the control rod, the ends of the fixed-springs attached to ground were no longer held in place by gravity. Although this meant that the prototype's behaviour would not be accurately predicted by the same constraints throughout its motion, it gave a defined point for transition to the final force-displacement path (after buckling), which wasn't achieved with the other prototypes.

All the mechanisms except the tied spring mechanism had the advantage that their behaviour could be altered by changing this distance of the additional side beams from the frame. This distance is labelled in Figure 39, which shows two views of the prototype.

Figure 39: The displacements of a realised spring and link model with a fixed-springs mechanism. Front and side views are shown for: under no load, pre-buckling, post-buckling, after buckling has completed.

This prototype was tested for a range of side beam positions. The quantitative results contained three distinct paths, as predicted in Figure 28. This was the first prototype to satisfy this behavioural criterion. An example of a result is shown in Figure 40(a). (b) shows these the three equilibrium paths overlaid on the result to allow easy comparison with the predicted result shown in Figure 28 (p.36).

Figure 40: (a) a test on the fixed spring prototype, with the additional side beams at a distance of 220mm from the frame; (b) the three paths contained within this result (using the colour scheme from Figure 28, p.36)

Not only do the straight lines fit very well to the above result, but the repeatability of the tests is shown by the similarity of the gradients of the three paths in each result:

Distance of side beams from frame / mm	200	210	220	230	240
Gradient of initial path (2dp)	0.40	0.39	0.37	0.40	0.40
Gradient of middle path (2dp)	0.25	0.26	0.25	0.27	0.25
Gradient of final path (2dp)	0.52	0.57	0.53	0.55	0.54

Table 4: A comparison of the gradients of the paths of the fixed-springs concepts with different initial spring lengths. The results for the two greatest distances of the additional side beams from the frame showed that for greater values of this distance, the equilibrium paths would exhibit significant jumps in the compressive load, demonstrating unwanted behaviour.

Therefore, the three advantages to this prototype were: its quantitative behaviour demonstrating three distinct equilibrium paths; the quantitative repeatability of the tests; and the ability to show unwanted dynamic jumps qualitatively, by simply changing the distance of the additional side beams from the frame – a task which could be easily done during a lecture.

The self-weight prototype

The three prototypes attempt to provide the behaviour given by the theoretical z-springs. It was found that if the rig was laid flat without any mechanism attached, the self-weight of the arch planks made the system’s qualitative behaviour the same as that of an unstable theoretical model. This was advantageous, as the other prototypes had not allowed unstable equilibrium paths to be shown, although it did not attempt to imitate the theoretical mechanism. The behaviour is shown in Figure 41:

Figure 41: A realised spring and link model with no mechanism present, but only the arch’s self-weight acting.

This approach used one new method. An extra steel rod was attached between the two outer x-springs’ rods, adjacent to the fixed travelling rod. This was attached using two left-over end-clamps. The function of this rod was to support the arch before buckling, giving the arch an adjustable initial angle. This angle was required because for the arch to buckle out of the x-y plane, it had to experience a force out of this plane. This was provided by an initial angle as the compressive force within the arch acted along the planks, whose direction now had a component in the z-direction.

The behaviour of this setup closely resembled that required by the qualitative design criteria. However, the same difficulty was encountered as in all the other mechanisms, which was that the arch did not completely buckle within the possible displacement of the outer x-springs from their initial free position. This is an inherent problem due to the dimensions of the springs and rig. The planks could be made shorter to solve the problem, but it is thought that they are currently at a minimal length to be clearly seen in a lecture theatre. Another solution would be to make the rest of the model larger, but this would stop the model being portable. A final solution is to keep all components the same apart from the x-springs. The central two springs could be replaced by one of half their length, to give the same overall force whilst sacrificing the balancing effect given by having two parallel to each other. This would allow all the x-springs to be of the same length, doubling the length of the current outer x-springs, and doubling their possible displacement. This would allow sufficient displacement for the arch to fold completely and for a third distinct equilibrium path to be taken after folding.

6.6 Conclusions

The fixed-springs prototype was shown to be the best imitation of the spring and link mechanism when following a stable equilibrium path. The test results showed that the three paths strongly resembled those predicted. This is a considerable achievement as it shows that the assumptions of the theoretical mechanism are also valid for the fixed-springs prototype, even though the assumptions neglect some real-world forces, such as weight and friction. However, the self-weight prototype was the only one able to show unstable equilibrium paths. These two prototypes could be easily switched between in a lecture by removing or adding the fixed-springs mechanism, and would therefore make very suitable teaching aids in their present state, with no further work required.

6.7 Further work

The slider concept has the advantage over all other designs that it is visually very similar to the theoretical mechanism. It has been difficult to use in a prototype, due to its large friction forces. However, clamping the rods in the slider's clamps, rather than the clamps at the fold's hinge, may reduce the friction significantly because the initial direction of movement of the unfixed clamp would be parallel to the rod, rather than perpendicular to it. This could be attempted to make the slider concept feasible in a prototype.

Furthermore, any prototype used in a lecture could be easily secured against the side of a flat surface using bars hanging down from the two corners of the frame at the end containing the control rod. When a force is applied to the control rod, these would resist the motion of the frame in the direction of the force by pressing against the side of the flat surface. This could be achieved using the holes which were proposed to allow bars to support the frame for demonstrating the tied arch in lectures.

7. Project Conclusions

The tied arch prototype and the ‘fixed-springs’ and ‘self-weight’ versions of the spring and link prototypes showed very similar qualitative behaviour to that predicted by elastic stability theory, making them very suitable for use in demonstrations. The ‘fixed-springs’ prototype showed accurate quantitative behaviour too. These achievements are particularly significant when viewed in the light of the unrealistic assumptions taken in the analyses of their initial mechanisms. The prototypes will aid students’ understanding and enjoyment of the subject greatly. They demonstrate the effects of instability dramatically, providing sufficient evidence to future engineers and scientists that elastic stability theory must be applied with care to avoid the dangerous consequences of elastic instability.

The investigation into the buckling behaviour of arches has added to Roorda’s research by providing a set of results found under different conditions, and by comparing the results to theory. Furthermore, the quantitative results of all the experiments are well predicted by elastic stability theory, providing new evidence to support the use of the theoretical mechanisms to show the generic behaviour of real-world structures, and the use of Elastic Stability Theory to predict the behaviour of elastic structures.

Temporal and economic constraints were managed effectively to achieve the project’s aims.

8. Future work

This report has provided a framework for the design and manufacture of other mechanisms which are used in the lecture series. In particular, many of the components of those used to explain symmetric and asymmetric bifurcations have already been designed and manufactured. In addition, a prototype of the Augusti mechanism would enrich students’ understanding of interactive bending very much, particularly as they could easily operate it in turn and feel small changes in forces which give large displacements. This could be easily constructed using the current components, and possibly a socket joint, as outlined in ‘The spring mechanism’ section (p.14).

The project has also posed many unanswered questions, which could be investigated by future fourth year students. Many of the questions provide inspiration for continuing the investigation of the buckling behaviour of steel strips. Recommendations have been made to allow Roorda’s research to be imitated and extended. Furthermore, the evidence for the importance of the mode shapes adopted by the steel strips has provided motivation for investigating how their mode shapes could be controlled to improve a structure’s strength, and for investigating the conditions under which flipping between mode shapes occurs, giving a significant reduction in a structure’s strength.

Finally, a natural progression of the work would be to investigate how the buckling of a plate compares to the behaviour of the spring and link mechanism and prototypes.

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10. Appendix: Risk Assessment

Risk Assessment ^{Form} Use of Computer Workstation

In Building General

Assessment undertaken Peter Charlton

Signed *Peter Charlton* Date: 27th October 2009

Assessment supervisor Paul Taylor

Signed *P.H. Taylor* Date: 28th October 2009

Hazard	Persons at Risk	Risk Controls In Place	Further Action Necessary To Control Risk
Eyestrain	Self	Take regular breaks of 10 mins per hour. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Look at distant objects - Adjust screen location to prevent glare or bright reflections - Ensure no screen flicker 	
Back Pain	Self	Ensure chair back is properly adjusted <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Exercise muscles 	
Aching shoulders, wrists	Self	Check seat height: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Forearms horizontal, level with top of desk - Keep wrists straight, use wrist rest - No overreaching, exercise muscles 	Consult supervisor and advice Departmental Safety Officer if any problems persist
Aching neck	Self	Check screen height <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Eyes level with top of screen, use document holder - Exercise muscles 	
Aching legs	Self	Check space under desk to stretch legs, feet rest comfortably on the floor, otherwise use footrest. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Exercise muscles 	
240V VAC Electric shock	Self	Equipment PAT tested by electronics	

E-mail Address: peter.charlton@hertford.ox.ac.uk

Checked by: *Peter Charlton*

date: 05/05/2010

Risk Assessment Operation of Machines during Construction process

In Building Thom – 4th Floor – DBT Laboratory

Assessment undertaken Peter Charlton Signed *Peter Charlton* Date: 27th October 2009

Assessment supervisor Paul Taylor Signed *P.A. Taylor* Date: 28th October 2009

Hazard	Persons at Risk	Risk Controls In Place	Further Action Necessary To Control Risk
<u>Operation of Drilling Machine</u>	Operator, other technicians, self, visiting persons	Minimum standards of protective clothing, hygiene and eye protection. Follow workshop rules. Training requirements in safe operation. Stop, start and emergency stop.	One operator to use. Any observers to stand clear.
- Entrapment and ejection		Appropriate guarding and clamping systems fitted to prevent entrapment and ejection	-
<u>Operation of Band Saw</u>	Operator, other technicians, self, visiting persons	Minimum standards of protective clothing, hygiene and eye protection. Follow workshop rules. Training requirements in safe operation.	One operator to use. Any observers to stand clear.
- Laceration of hands		Use of pushing devices to advance work piece through the saw. Full length blade guard covering the non-used portion of the blade.	-
- Inhalation of dust		Use of face masks and special high filter vacuum cleaner	-
- Installation of saw blade	Operator, technicians, self	Only skilled workshop staff allowed to change blades. In this instance, follow workshop procedures	-

E-mail Address: peter.charlton@hertford.ox.ac.uk

Checked by: *P.A. Taylor*

date: 28.10.09

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